

View of an Eyeshot on Mriddbhakshanjanya Pandu in Ayurveda

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ABSTRACT: Pandu Roga is a disease described in Ayurveda since immemorial, the first reference found in Vedas. Most of the Acharyas have described five types of Pandu Roga, i.e. Vatika, Paittika, Kaphaja, Tridoshaja, and Mridabhakshhanya Pandu. Acharya Charaka, Vagbhatta, and Madhava have given a kind of Mridakabhakshanjanya of Pandu. Mridabhakshhanya Pandu has a worldwide distribution, but the highest prevalence occurs in tropical & sub-tropical regions and areas with inadequate sanitation, Poverty, ignorance, lack of hygiene maintenance, bad sanitation and use of uncooked food or improper washing of food materials, eating soil, etc. are the important factors for spreading Mridabhakshhanya Pandu in developing countries like India. When consumed, mud does not get digested in amashaya and blocks the rasavaha strotas. Due to this, gradually rasa dhatu kshaya takes place and in turn, the subsequent dhatu are not properly nourished, thereby producing Pandu roga.

KEYWORDS: Mrudbhakshanjanya pandu, Pandu, Acharya Charaka.

INTRODUCTION

Pandu Roga is a disease described in Ayurveda since immemorial, the first reference found in Vedas. Pandu Roga references are found in Rigveda and Atharvaveda.

The word Pandu is derived from 'Padi Nashane' Dhatu by adding 'ku' Pratyaya to it, the meaning of which is always taken in the sense of Nashana and as Pandu has been kept under the group which is classified and named according to the change in color. In the opinion of Sabdarnava 'Pandustu peetbhagardh ketaki dhulisannibham^[1]. The detailed description of Pandu Roga and its classification starts from Ayurvedic Samhitas only. Most of the Acharyas accepted the disease under five categories Vataja, Pittaja, Kaphaja, Sannipataja, and Mridabhakshanjanya. This type of Pandu has been described in detail by Acharya Charak, Vagbhatta, and Madhava Nidan^[2-4]. Acharya Susruta did not mention Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu and explained that Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu may be included in Vatadi Dosha^[5]. But Acharya Charaka and Vagbhatta including Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu separately may be the specific treatment advised for it. In Harita Samhita Rukshana Pandu appear of Mriddabhakshanjanya Pandu^[6].

Nidana

- Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu develops in one who is prone to eating soil. Many times, the soil is eaten by young children and by the elderly too due to ignorance. Describing the varieties of pica Charaka recognizes three types of picas i.e. kashaya, Lavana rasa, and madhura. Soil eating gives rise to three types of Pandu-. Vatika, Paittika and Kaphaja.

The habit of eating.

- kashay quality of pica- vitiate Vata dosha
- Lavana rasa quality of pica- vitiate pitta dosha
- madhura quality of eating pica- vitiate Kapha dosha^[7-9].

The most predominant causative factor of this type of Pandu is soil eating. Chakrapani says, that despite its association with doshas, it is named by Prithvi and not dosha because the former prescribes specific symptoms and treatment^[10]. Harita has referred to Mridbhakshanjanya pandu Roga as Rukshanah Prokta, referring to the main pathogenesis occurring in it i.e. it causes dryness in the body^[11]. Harita also explained the ras and gunas of Bhoomi.

Krishna Bhoomi is Madhura and Ruksha in quality

Peeta Varna Bhoomi is Kashaya in Rasa

Rakta Varna Bhoomi is Tikta in Rasa

Shweta (Sita) Bhoomi is Madhura-Amla in Rasa

Neela Bhoomi is Katu in Rasa.^[12]

Yogindranatha Sen says that in Susruta the type caused by earth-eating is included in Doshaja types.^[13]

Sampriti-

Soil enters Amashaya it makes the Dhatus ruksha, also This soil doesn't digest by 'Jatharagni' as well as dhatwagni for the Pachana and it blocks the channels of rasavahsrotas & an obstruction in other Srotas not to allow any physiologically needful substance to pass through. Hence successive dhatu is not nourished, and rakta is not also formed. The lack of blood causes panduvarna. Because of this, the Indriyas of the Patient become weaker to receive their own Arthas properly and genuinely. This also damages Saptadhatu(satva) & Jathragni^[14-16]. Blood is a very important dhatu of the body. Hence lack of blood causes loss of stamina, color, tejas, ojas, perception power of sense organs, digestion, etc.

Rupa-^[17-19]

The Features of this type of Pandu are-

Pandunetra - mutra - nakha (pallor conjunctiva – urine-nails)

Shuna ganda, akshikuta, bhru (Swelling in the cheeks, eyelids, and eyebrows)

krumikoshtha (no. of intestinal parasites in stool)

Padanabhimehanshuna (swelling of the feet, naval region, and penis)

Sasruk Kaphanvitam (Stool being associated with blood and mucus)

Atisara (Loose motion)

Agni nasha (destruction of digestion capacity)

Balanasha (destruction of strength)

Varna nasha (destruction of color)

Veeryanasha (destruction of the potency of the body)

Indriybalanash (destruction of the strength of sense organs.)

Tejonash (destruction of the heating element of the body)

Ojanash (destruction of the essence of tissues.

Cardinal Symptoms:

akshikoot shotha, Pedal edema, Agnimandya, Fever, pallor of eye and skin.

gudkandu,krimi darshana in stool by patient.

Sr.	Lakshana	Charaka[17]	Vagbhatta[18]	Madhavnidana [19]
I.	Bala kshaya	✓	-	-
II.	Krimi koshtha	✓	-	-
III.	Pada shotha	✓	✓	✓
IV.	Mehana shotha	✓	✓	✓
V.	Akshikuta shotha	✓	-	-
VI.	Ganda shotha	✓	✓	✓

VII.	Nabhi shotha	✓	-	-
VIII.	Purisha sakrimi	-	✓	-
IX.	Atisara	-	-	✓
X.	Purisha sakapha	✓	✓	✓
XI.	Ananna Sophha	-	-	✓
XII.	Asya shotha	✓	✓	✓
XIII.	Arsha	-	-	✓

The symptoms described by Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu Roga mainly relate to the development of worms in the gastrointestinal tract and the development of Oedema in the different parts of the body resulting in the passage of excess stools or stool combined with blood and mucus.^[20]

According to Acharya Jejjata, Krimikosthata (worm infestation) is present as a common feature of all Pandu rogas. But other's opinion is this symptom is only related to Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu. In the opinion of Videha, soil consumption gives rise to symptoms such as paleness of the body lassitude, and drowsiness. Emaciation of the body Dyspnoea, cough, swelling of feet and hands, emaciation, piles, a weak digestive fire depression, and distaste^[21].

DISCUSSION

The features described by Acharya Charaka mainly fall under three headings-Oedema in various body parts (peri-orbital, pedal, umbilical, and genital); development of worms in the abdomen; and passage of loose stools and stools associated with mucous and blood. Most of these symptoms are correlated with worm infestation. The oedema in the various body parts may also be associated with the malnourishment caused by the worm interfering with digestion and absorption.

People who are in contact with soil stand a high chance of getting intestinal worms.

Also, persons with-

1. Poor hygiene
2. Who moves on the ground barefoot
3. Habit of eating soil-contaminated food on the street.
4. Eating food using hands contaminated with soil and dust.

Scientifically accepted as the cause of anemia due to worm infestation and consequent blood loss. These worms suck blood from the mucosa of the intestine and then they leave the site which continues to bleed. Women with PICA have also been associated with vitamin deficiency of folate, and B12 along with that of iron in a study ranging to the extent of 82.4%, 41.2%, and 70.6% respectively^[22]. Depending upon the Doshas, different types of treatment should be given to the patient suffering from Mridabhakshanjanya Pandu. Due to a special cause of disease special treatment like Tikshna shodhan is advised in such cases. After shodhana, the patient should be given different types of medications. A specific formulation for causing aversion to soil has been described by Acharya Charak which consists of soil Siddha with Vidanga, Ativisha, Neem-leaf, Ela Pathya, Katurohini, and Kutaja^[23].

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